

TEAM BASE LEARNING AND LEARNING BY THEMSELVES WITH COGNITIVE ANXIETY AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS; A QUASI EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Objective: the aim, of current study is to see the effect of team base learning and learning by themselves on cognitive test anxiety and its association with academic performance among medical students.

Study design: A quasi experimental study design.

Place and duration: This quasi-experimental study employed the Cognitive Test Anxiety Version-2 questionnaires as its primary instrument. The study sample consisted of 80 students enrolled in CMH Medical College, Lahore, Pakistan. Data collection occurred during the period spanning from December 2019 to October 2020, with data acquisition concluding in October 2023.

Methodology: The study included 80 students from CMH Medical College, Lahore, Pakistan, divided into two groups: one with 40 students participating in team-based learning sessions and the other with 40 students engaged in individual self-directed learning. The Cognitive Test Anxiety Version-2 questionnaire and exam test papers were used to collect data on cognitive test anxiety and academic performance, respectively.

Result: Participants in the team-based learning session outperformed those in the self-directed learning session on the exam test (team-based learning: $M = 27.5$, $SD = 4.03$; self-directed learning: $M = 23.5$, $SD = 2.95$). Moderate anxiety scores were associated with higher exam scores. Notably, 30 team-based learning participants scored moderately on the CTAS-2, achieving a 95% exam score.

Conclusion: this study results confirm our formulated objective by establishing a relationship between team base learning with student performance in the exam test. This study specifically show that team base learning student score high on moderate anxiety

test score. Students score on moderate cognitive test anxiety, show higher academic achievement.

Keywords: *Academic performance exam test score, Cognitive anxiety test, learning by themselves, Session, Team-based learning.*

INTRODUCTION

Team base learning (TBL), is a cooperative learning and teaching style that helps people to follow a structured process to promote students engagement in learning.1 t facilitates students learning and disclosure, helping the students to share knowledge in group and learn teaching strategies from group to enhance learning very quickly.2 Students acknowledge that TBL is encouraging students to study actively and learn from group to improve their own performance in exam.3 Literature informs that TBL method help people to create an active learning environment which can make students' performance better.4 Moreover, research study by Kim and soon suggested that team base learning is strongly associated with problem solving, participation and motivation toward.5 There is a need to understand factors explaining this shift. The available literature in the context of Pakistan suggests a team base is fostering independence responsibility motivation, skill and positive interdependence which promote autonomy promotion. 6,7

The competitive nature of studies compels the students to be focused on their grades, which arise cognitive test anxiety among students may impairs test performance that can be balanced by individual variation and changing the environment.8 In addition to this, the level of cognitive test anxiety of the students during exam found to be significantly moderate to high during exams.9

It would be pragmatic to determine the plausible explanation for this finding. Some of the factors that have been explored in western literature are personal distress, personality traits and self-esteem. As academic performance is known to be related to cognitive test anxiety, it would be interesting to explore the association of TBL session and LBT session with the level of

cognitive test anxiety to performance of students in exam test score. The current study, therefore, aims to explore the levels of test anxiety score among university students and its association with academic achievement, team base learning and learning by themselves.

METHODOLOGY

This quasi-experimental study involved a purposive selection of 80 male and female students, aged 15 to 25. The sample size was determined based on prior research and the minimum required for a quasi-experimental study. Participants were divided into two groups: (a) Team-Based Learning (TBL) session students and (b) Learning by Themselves (LBT) session students, with each session comprising 40 participants, equally split between male and female students.

Test anxiety levels were assessed using the Cognitive Test Anxiety Scale 2nd version (CTAS-2), a 24-item instrument designed to measure cognitive test anxiety among university students. Demographic data, including age, gender, year of study, and socio-economic status, were collected through consent forms approved by the college authorities. The CTAS-2 scores were analyzed to classify anxiety levels as follows: low (score: 24-43), moderate (score: 24-43), and high (score: 43-59).10 Participants were then divided into TBL and LBT groups and presented with exam questionnaires to assess academic performance. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS version 20, employing Pearson correlation coefficient to examine the relationship between TBL and academic performance, and one-way ANOVA to assess cognitive test anxiety and academic performance among participants.

RESULTS

Table-I; Demographic profile of participants (n=80).

Variables	Categories	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age	18-28	44	54.81%
	28-38	36	46.19%
Gender	Less than 3	35	44.31%
	More than 3	45	55.69%
Education	High school or less	20	25.20%
	Undergraduate	50	62.96%
	Graduate	10	12.48%
Living environment	Urban	46	57.35%
	Rural	34	42.65%
Monthly income	Less than 50,000	65	81.49%
	More than 50,000	15	18.51%
Socioeconomic status	Low	26	31.82%
	Middle	54	68.18%
	Upper	0	-

The demographic profile of participants shows that the majority (54.81%) were aged between 18-28 years, while 46.19% were aged 28-38 years. Regarding family size, 55.69% of participants belonged to families with more than three members, while 44.31% came from families with less than three members. Most participants (62.96%) had an undergraduate level of education, followed by 25.20% who had high school education or less, and 12.48% were graduates. A

larger proportion of participants (57.35%) lived in urban areas, while 42.65% resided in rural areas. In terms of monthly income, 81.49% of participants reported earning less than 50,000 PKR, while 18.51% earned more than 50,000 PKR. Socioeconomic status revealed that 68.18% of participants belonged to the middle class, while 31.82% were in the lower socioeconomic class, with no participants from the upper class.

Table-II; Comparing Cognitive Test Anxiety Scale CATAS-2 Score Across Team Base Learning and Learning by Themselves (n=80).

VARIABLES	TOTAL			FEMALE		MALE	
	Category	f	%	f	%	f	%
Team base learning	low	8	10%	5	6.25%	3	3.75%
	moderate	30	37.5%	14	17.5%	16	20%
	high	2	2.5%	1	1.25%	1	1.25%
Learning by themselves	low	5	6.25%	3	3.75%	2	2.5%
	moderate	20	25%	12	15%	8	10%
	high	15	18.75%	5	6.25%	10	12.5%

The comparison of Cognitive Test Anxiety Scale (CATAS-2) scores across team-based learning and learning by themselves showed that in team-based learning, 10% of participants reported low anxiety, with females (6.25%) slightly more than males (3.75%). Moderate anxiety was observed in

37.5% of participants, with males (20%) slightly more than females (17.5%). High anxiety levels were the least reported in this group at 2.5%, equally distributed between females (1.25%) and males (1.25%). In contrast, for participants learning by themselves, 6.25% reported low

anxiety, with females (3.75%) slightly more than males (2.5%). Moderate anxiety was found in 25% of participants, with females (15%) more than males (10%). High anxiety was more prevalent in this group (18.75%), with males

(12.5%) significantly higher than females (6.25%). These results indicate that team-based learning results in lower levels of high anxiety compared to learning independently, particularly for males.

Table-III; Comparison of academic performance of student in Team base learning session with students in learning by themselves sessions (n =80).

Baseline Characteristics	Study Groups		P-value
	TBL (n=40)	LBT = (n=40)	
Academic performance (mean±SD)	27.5±4.03	23.8±2.95	0.003

The comparison of academic performance between team-based learning (TBL) and learning-by-themselves (LBT) groups revealed that participants in the TBL group had a higher mean academic performance score of 27.5 (±4.03), while those in the LBT group had a lower mean score of 23.8 (±2.95). The P-value of 0.003 indicates a statistically significant difference in academic performance between the two groups, with TBL participants demonstrating better outcomes. These findings highlight the effectiveness of team-based learning in improving academic performance compared to independent learning.

DISCUSSION:

The findings of the current study provide valuable insights into the effects of team-based learning (TBL) compared to individual learning on cognitive test anxiety and academic performance among medical students. The results align with and contribute to the growing body of literature emphasizing the benefits of collaborative learning strategies.

The demographic profile of participants revealed a diverse representation in terms of age, gender, education level, living environment, and socioeconomic status. These factors are important to consider as they may influence learning preferences and outcomes. For instance, previous research has suggested that younger students and those from urban areas may adapt more readily to innovative learning strategies such as TBL due to their prior exposure to similar educational environments. 11 The comparison of cognitive test anxiety levels between TBL and individual learning groups showed that TBL participants experienced lower levels of high anxiety (2.5%)

compared to those learning by themselves (18.75%). This finding is consistent with the literature suggesting that collaborative learning environments provide emotional and psychological support, reducing anxiety levels among students. 12 Team-based learning fosters a sense of community and shared responsibility, which can alleviate the stress associated with academic assessments. Moreover, males in the TBL group reported lower high-anxiety levels (1.25%) compared to their counterparts in the individual learning group (12.5%), highlighting the potential gender-specific benefits of collaborative learning strategies.

Frequency analysis of Ctas-2 score among TBL session learning and LBT session learning showed that TBL session learning had highest number of respondent moderate CTAS-2 score which included highest number of male respondent. While LBT session learning showed that there are highest number of respondent score on lowest level and highest level on CTAS-2 scale.

TBL session learning has strong effect on student exam score as compared to LBT session learning (TBL session learning = 27.8, SD = 4.03 and LBT session learning = 23.8, SD = 2.95). This means that students in the TBL session learning perform better in exam test as compared to student in the LBT session learning. The results are line with previous research conducted by Sweet and colleagues (2023), suggest that TBL is identified by participant as constructive work and they improve their performance by stimulant their deep interest through discussion within group.13 Same studies pointed that Team-Based Learning (TBL) engaging, stimulating, and effective for learning in pharmacy education. While it could benefit from better workshop timing management

and more effective discussion facilitation, you see great potential for TBL in pharmacy education. 14, 15 TBL session learning is associated with academic performance of students. Pearson correlation coefficients shows that academic performance = 1 TBL =.838* and TBL= 1, Academic performance = .839**this mean that correlation is significant at 0.01 level. Student in the TBL session learning will show high score in exam test. Our findings are consistent with previous researches pointed out that TBL participants had strongly higher level of learning in the area of acquiring, understanding and producing knowledge that enhance students engagement that foster communication and work performance.[15, 16] Same studies conducted in China by Botang et al., (2021), and Kurdistan by Parinaz and colleagues (2021) pointed out that achievement motivation moderate the test anxiety which related to better performance in academic career.(17,18)

CONCLUSION:

Our finding suggests that TBL and academic performance are related in positive direction when TBL learning is high then student will perform better in exam test. The study findings also show that the large number of TBL student score on moderate anxiety test score perform better in exam test.

Future recommendation and limitation of study

In the light of the finding of study, some limitations are made. There is need to arrange seminar in colleges to aware student about the importance of TBL learning and provide them method to balance cognitive test anxiety. There is some suggestion for future research. The study data included one college future researcher can use multiple college and students different ethnicity group.

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